

Article:

Synthesis, X-Ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy, Differential Thermal Analysis and Magnetic Susceptibility of the alloy $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ with $x = 0.5$

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Abstract

Polycrystalline samples of the alloy $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ with $x = 0.5$ were prepared by the melt and anneal method and characterized by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA), and Magnetic Susceptibility (MS) techniques. It was found that this alloy is composed of two main phases, one poor and another rich in Ta, and traces of TaSe_2 . The sample shows a weak ferromagnetic behavior with $T_c > 300$ K, a characteristic that can be useful for room-temperature ferromagnetic devices.

Keywords: semiconductors; alloys, crystal structure, RT-ferromagnetism.

Artículo:

Síntesis, difracción de rayos X, microscopía electrónica de barrido, análisis térmico diferencial y susceptibilidad magnética de la aleación $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ con $x = 0.5$

Resumen

Muestras policristalinas de la aleación $x = 1/2$ del sistema $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ fueron preparadas por el método de fusión y recocido, caracterizándolas por las técnicas de Difracción de Rayos X (DRX), Microscopía Electrónica de Barrido (MEB), Análisis Térmico Diferencial (ATD) y Susceptibilidad Magnética (SM). Se encontró que las muestras contienen dos fases principales, una pobre y otra rica en Ta, y trazas de TaSe_2 . La muestra presenta un comportamiento ferromagnético débil con $T_c > 300$ K, característica que puede ser útil para dispositivos ferromagnéticos a temperatura ambiente.

Palabras claves: semiconductores; aleaciones; estructura cristalina; ferromagnetismo a temperatura ambiente.

1 Introduction

(I-III-VI₂)/(TM-VI) alloys have been studied in recent years [1]-[26] to create new materials for spintronics and room temperature ferromagnetism applications, in analogy with parent II-IV-V₂/III-V alloys [28]-[37]. In addition, an unusual superconductor behavior observed in CuCo₂InS₄ [25] and CuInNbTe₃ [26] has opened a new research perspective for these alloys.

The substitution of I or III cation by a TM-atom in the cationic sublattice of the ordered chalcopyrite crystal structure of I-III-VI₂ compounds (space group $I\bar{4}2d$) produce a gradual disorder that induces a structural transition to the semi-ordered chalcopyrite-like structure (space group $P\bar{4}2c$). This gradual crystal structure transition takes place during a large composition range.

Figure 1: Structural phase transitions for (I-III-VI₂)_{1-x}(TM-VI)_x alloys. For better comprehension (CuInSe₂)_{1-x}(FeSe)_x alloys have been taken as an example. At the left side of the figure, the ordered chalcopyrite structure of CuInSe₂. At the center, the semiordered chalcopyrite-like structure, for compositions $0 < x < 2/3$; the orange atom represents the crystallographic site which is shared by the three cations. On the right side, the reordered stannite structure; observe the TM layers

(I-III-VI₂)/(TM-VI) alloys can be represented by the equation (I-III-VI₂)_{1-x}(TM-VI)_x where x is the composition range. If that is the case, for $x = 2/3$, the number of TM-atoms equals the number of I and III-atoms. It had been observed that, at this composition value, a new reordering occurs [21, 22, 23], then, the $P\bar{4}2c$ structure transits to the ordered stannite $I\bar{4}2d$ crystal structure. Figure 1 is

a representation of the crystal structure sequence, taken (CuInSe₂)_{1-x}(FeSe)_x alloys as an example.

An exception to this general behavior has been observed in alloys where Ta is the TM-atom. In the (CuAlSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x and (CuGaSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x alloy systems, an intermediate hexagonal phase (space group) analogous to the Cu_{0.52}TaSe₂ phase but with the Cu site shared with Al (Ga), merges at $x > 0.2$ due to the low solubility of Ta in the ternary alloy [22, 23, 24]. (Cu-III)_{0.5}TaSe₂ (III: Al, Ga) phases are topological 2D-layer types and can be defined as a TaSe₂-like phase. TaSe₂ is a rather complex system, with many polytypic forms. It has been investigated due to the interest because of the presence of charge density wave phenomena (CDW) encountered in this compound [27].

From the magnetic point of view, I-III-VI₂ compounds are diamagnetic; the exchange of I and/or III-atoms for TM-atoms in the ternary chalcopyrite matrix induces a variety of magnetic effects. Because of their electronic structure (Ar 3d⁵ 4s²), Mn²⁺ has been used extensively as TM for (I-III-VI₂)/(TM-VI) alloys; at low concentrations (less than 5 %) Mn substitution is paramagnetic with a little coupling of Mn²⁺ moments but at higher Mn²⁺ concentration appears antiferromagnetic coupling [38, 39, 40]. However, for the CuGaTe₂/MnTe system, the magnetic character could be accounted for the formation of Mn²⁺-containing superparamagnetic clusters [41] corroborated by EPR measurements [14]. A similar superparamagnetic behavior has been observed in Cu(In,Ga)FeTe₃ [42], (CuInSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x [43], (CuGaSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x [24], (CuAlSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x [22] and (CuInTe₂)_{1-x}(TaTe)_x [44] alloy systems.

In this work, we are reporting the synthesis and characterization of the alloy $x = 1/2$ that belongs to the (CuAlSe₂)_{1-x}(TaSe)_x alloy system with emphasis on the identification of the intermediate hexagonal phase and the magnetic behavior.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Synthesis

Samples have been produced by the melt and anneal method as is described below. Starting materials (Cu, Al, Ta, and Te with nominal purity of

99.99 wt. %) in the stoichiometric ratio were mixed in an evacuated (10^{-4} Torr) and sealed quartz tube with the inner walls previously carbonized to prevent the chemical reaction of the elements with quartz. The ampoule was heated until 490 K (melting point of Se) keeping this temperature for 48 h and shaking all the time using an electromechanical motor. This procedure guarantees the formation of binary species at low temperatures avoiding the existence of free Se at high temperatures, which could produce Se deficiency in the ingot. Then the temperature was slowly increased until 1423 K, with the mechanical shaker always connected for better mixing of the components. After 24 h, the cooling cycle begins descending the temperature down to 800 K (the annealing temperature) with the mechanical shaker off. The ampoule is keeping at the annealing temperature for 30 days to guarantee a good thermal equilibrium for X-ray diffraction measurements and then the furnace is switching off to room temperature.

2.2 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray powder diffraction data were collected employing a diffractometer (Siemens D5005) equipped with a graphite monochromator ($\text{CuK}\alpha$, $\lambda = 1.54059 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV and 20 mA. Silicon powder was used as an external standard. The samples were scanned from $10 - 100^\circ 2\theta$, with a step size of 0.02° and a counting time of 20 s. The Bruker analytical software was used to establish the positions of the peaks from the $\text{CuK}\alpha_2$ component and to strip mathematically the $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ components from each reflection. The peak positions were extracted employing a single-peak profile fitting carried out through the Bruker DIFFRACplus software. Each reflection was modeled utilizing a pseudo-Voigt function.

2.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Stoichiometric relations were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique, using Hitachi S2500 equipment. The microchemical composition was found by an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDS) coupled with a computer-based

multichannel analyzer (MCA, Delta III analysis, and Quantex software, KeveX). For the EDS analysis, $\text{K}\alpha$ lines were used. The accelerating voltage was 15 kV. The samples were tilted 35 degrees. A standardless EDS analysis was made with a relative error of $\pm(5 - 10)\%$ and detection limits of the order of 0.3 wt %, where the k-ratios are based on theoretical standards.

2.4 Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA)

Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) measurements were carried out in a fully automatic Perkin-Elmer apparatus, which consists of a Khantal resistance furnace ($T_{\text{max}} = 1650 \text{ K}$) equipped with Pt/Pt-Rh thermocouples and an informatics system for the automatic acquisition data. The internal standard used was a high purity (99.99 wt. %) piece of gold. The temperature runs have been performed from ambient temperature to 1400-1500 K, which is the recommended operative limit. The heating rate was controlled electronically to 20 K h^{-1} ; the cooling rate was given by the natural cooling of the furnace after switching off. Transition temperatures were manually obtained from the ΔT vs. T graph with the criteria that the transition occurs at the intersection of the baseline with the slope of the thermal transition peak. The maximum error committed in the determination of transition temperatures by this method was estimated to be $\pm 10 \text{ K}$.

2.5 Magnetic susceptibility

DC magnetic susceptibility as a function of temperature measurements, $\chi(T)$, was performed on a Quantum Design SQUID magnetometer, equipped with a superconducting magnet able to produce fields up to 5 T. Samples in the form of powder were compacted with a piece of cotton inside the sample holder to prevent any movement. Zero-field-cooling and field cooling (ZFC-FC) measurements were carried out in the temperature range 2–300 K using the standard method of cooling the sample to the lowest temperature (usually 2 K) without applied magnetic field, then heating the sample to room temperature applying a little magnetic field

Table 1: Measured stoichiometry of the alloy $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ with $x = 0.5$

Composition (x)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Nominal stoichiometry (% Atom)		Experimental stoichiometry (% Atom)	
		CuAlSe ₂ -like phase	(Cu _{0.52} TaSe ₂)-like phase	CuAlSe ₂ -like phase	(Cu _{0.52} TaSe ₂)-like phase
$x = 1/2$	249.18	Cu = 16.67	Cu = 07.4	Cu = 19.3 ± 0.3	Cu = 09.8 ± 0.3
		Al = 16.67	Al = 07.4	Al = 19.7 ± 0.3	Al = 07.0 ± 0.5
		Ta = 16.67	Ta = 28.4	Ta = 05.7 ± 0.5	Ta = 29.8 ± 0.4
		Se = 50.00	Se = 56.8	Se = 55.3 ± 0.7	Se = 53.4 ± 0.6

29.8 ± 0.4 % atoms of Ta, and 53.4 ± 0.6 % atoms of Se which is in good agreement with the calculated nominal stoichiometry for this phase. The Cu atoms represent 58.3 % and Al the 41.7 % of the atoms in the 2i site, in consequence, the stoichiometry of the sample can be written as $(\text{Cu}_{0.30}\text{Al}_{0.22})\text{TaSe}_2$.

Figure 4: Microphotography of the hexagonal $\text{Cu}_{0.30}\text{Al}_{0.22}\text{TaSe}_2$ phase

The microphotography of the $(\text{Cu}_{0.30}\text{Al}_{0.22})\text{TaSe}_2$ phase in Figure 4 shows the 2D-laminar character of this phase, characteristic of other Ta-rich phases [22].

Finally, in Figure 5, the mass magnetic susceptibility of sample $x = 1/2$ is displayed. The sample is a weak ferromagnetic with a critical temperature $T_c > 300$ K. The hystereses between ZFC and FC curves evidence the presence of magnetic nanoclusters. An additional magnetic contribution at low temperature, for $T < 27$ K, is due to the size of the nanoclusters. In the temperature interval, $2 < T < 27$ K, the nanoclusters unblock at

Figure 5: Mass magnetic susceptibility of sample $x = 1/2$ of the $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ alloy system

different temperatures depending on their size up to $T \sim 27$ K where all the nanoclusters are unblocked. It is not possible, at the stage of this investigation, to elucidate the contribution of each of the two phases in the alloy; the chalcopyrite-like phase has a much less amount of Ta than the hexagonal phase, in consequence, their contribution must be less important. The preparation of the hexagonal $\text{Cu}_{0.30}\text{Al}_{0.22}\text{TaSe}_2$ phase will be a task in the next future.

4 Conclusions

Polycrystalline samples with $x = 1/2$ of the $(\text{CuAlSe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{TaSe})_x$ alloy system have been synthesized and characterized by XRD, DTA, SEM, and MS techniques. It was found that the samples contain two main phases, one poor and another rich

in Ta, $(\text{CuAl})_{1.2}\text{Ta}_{0.3}\text{Se}_2$ and $(\text{Cu}_{0.30}\text{Al}_{0.22})\text{TaSe}_2$ respectively, and traces of TaSe_2 . The sample shows a weak ferromagnetic behavior with $T_c > 300$ K, a characteristic that can be useful for room-temperature ferromagnetic devices.

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